

Country report on Colombia

(ES12002: Coursework)

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Colombia Country Report

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Introduction

This report will provide an overview of Colombia; the current state of its economy, recent challenges it has weathered and some of the major macroeconomic problems facing the nation. Colombia is a nation in the northernmost reaches of South America, sharing borders with Ecuador, Brazil, Peru, Panama, and Venezuela and is home to 51 million people. It has a diverse economy with large exports of petroleum, gold, coal briquettes and coffee. Colombia has experienced strong trend growth since 2000, despite some major challenges, including some of the highest rates of organised crime in the world and the impacts of the Latin American crisis in the 1990s.

The macroeconomic state of Colombia today

Colombia is a country with high human development according to the UN with a HDI of 0.752 (ranking 88th), above Venezuela, but just below Brazil and Peru (UNDP, 2022). The Human Development Index (HDI) measures social and economic development in countries. It considers mean and expected years of schooling, life expectancy at birth and gross national income per capita. This is then aggregated into a single figure that can be used to compare countries' levels of development. The macroeconomic state of the country can be analysed through the main indicators of economic growth, price stability, the trade balance and levels of employment.

Figure 1 shows that the GDP of Colombia is currently \$343 billion (World Bank, 2022) which puts it in line with its neighbours such as Peru and it was close to Venezuela until Venezuela's economic crisis in the 2010s. However, it's still behind the largest economy in Latin America: Brazil.

GDP growth rates in Colombia per decade align closely with the growth rates of its neighbours, with the exception of the 1980s, when Colombia fared far better than others during a crisis that greatly affected the GDP of other South American countries, for example in 1989 the GDP growth rate of Peru was negative 12.31%. (World Bank, 2023a). Overall Colombia has seen relatively

stable growth in recent history and the economy has been growing consistently, except for several crises that will be examined later.

The GDP of Colombia can further be split into different components: consumption, investment, government spending and exports minus imports, illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 shows household consumption makes up 71.9% of GDP. Colombia is also running a trade deficit, with the value of exports being 7.2 percentage points of GDP less than imports.

The trade in goods in Colombia today is focused greatly on primary products, mainly oil and metals, as well as illegal narcotics. In fact, the two largest goods exports in the country are crude petroleum and cocaine. (Bloomberg, 2023).

Figure 4: Colombia's export treemap, Data from OEC (2021)

Crude petroleum production far exceeds domestic demand, making Colombia a net exporter of unrefined crude petroleum, exporting 552,000 barrels per day in 2020 (EIA, 2022).

However, Colombia is a net importer of refined petroleum products. In 2021, it imported \$3.18 billion but only exported \$2.14 billion (OEC, 2021). Crude oil is generally cheaper than refined oil products, so for a country that relies on the exports of crude oil heavily, it's potentially bottlenecking its economy as it doesn't have enough capacity - at 378,600 barrels a day (EIA, 2022) - to refine enough crude oil to meet domestic demand. Colombia must therefore import, which increases the trade deficit and can make the country reliant on other refined oil exporters.

A second major export for Colombia is cocaine. Colombia produces 70-80% of the world's cocaine (DEA, 2021) and it was projected to overtake revenues from oil, generating \$18.2 billion dollars in 2022 from exports. Cocaine makes up about 4% of the country's GDP (Bloomberg, 2023). However, this trade does not correspond to economic growth and prosperity, as farmers are paid around \$1 dollar per kilo of cocaine, but when that kilo reaches the USA, it could be worth up to \$200,000. The cocaine trade is unequal and top heavy, meaning that the poor who harvest the product rarely ever reap any significant income from it (Muchow, 2009).

The inflation rate for consumer goods is 11.4% (IMF, 2023). However, the central bank of Colombia has set an inflation target of 3% +/- 1% (Banrep, 2023). Although inflation had fallen to around this level during the 2010s, after Covid, inflation rose greatly to its current levels above 10%. However, the IMF predicts that this is temporary and that by 2025 inflation will be within the target range once again. (IMF, 2023).

Figure 5:
Annual percentage change in average consumer prices

Employment in Colombia

Figure 6 shows that 60.8% of Colombians between the ages of 15 and 64 are in employment, as of 2019. This number seemed to plateau between the 1950s and early 1980s before beginning to rise at the end of the decade. The percentage of employed Colombians peaked in 2015 at 65.4%. The unemployment rate in Colombia rose sharply during the pandemic, reaching around 16% in 2020, but has returned to pre pandemic levels, with it sitting at 10.5% in 2022 compared to 10.3% in 2019, according to The World Bank (2023). Despite the decrease post-pandemic, unemployment remains far higher than in neighbouring Ecuador (3.8%) and was higher even than Venezuela to the east at 7.5% in 2020, a sign that many of the issues Colombia is experiencing are at a national as opposed to regional level (The World Bank, 2023). Those that complete secondary education in the nation earn far higher salaries on average than people who have only primary education: Eliana Carranza (2022) suggests almost 30% more. They also have 1.5 times the likelihood of finding a waged job. Yet in 2019, almost 70% of unemployed citizens had undergone secondary or higher education. In a nation where only 56% of citizens have completed secondary education this illustrates a far higher rate of unemployment for those more highly educated, with 13.2% unemployment for people who have completed secondary education compared to only 7.7% of those who have failed to do so. (Eliana Carranza, 2022).

**Figure 6:
Employment In Colombia**

Data from Penn World Table (2023) and the UN Population Division Portal (2022)

Poverty and inequality in Colombia

According to Griffin (2023), 36.6% of Colombians were living in relative poverty in 2022, indicating a major issue with wealth distribution in a nation that also sees the highest differences in wealth between regions of nations for which the OECD holds data. In 2019, Colombia's Gini index stood at an extremely high 51.5 in 2021, making it the 9th most unequal country on Earth (World Bank, 2023). These gaps are arguably against the macroeconomic interests of the nation. Galor (2004) argues that income inequality can act as a destabilising factor, leading to social unrest. This may be a particular issue in Colombia given its already poor social cohesion; it ranks as the third worst nation for sense of community in the OECD database (OECD, 2023). Crime and poverty are intertwined, as illustrated by Fleming (2011), when the Gini index increases by 1 the rate of burglaries increases by eight per hundred thousand people. As such, the high rates of poverty in Colombia are likely to negatively impact the economy. Figure 7 shows Colombia's homicide rate to be 27.5 in 2021. Extreme rates of crime increase costs of doing business and deter local and international investment. The result is less investment, leading to lower growth rates than if poverty and as a result crime rates were lower.

Regional inequality is also a significant factor in Colombia's economy with it facing some of the highest differences in incomes between regions in the world: the richest 20% exceed the GDP per capita of the poorest 20% of regions by a factor of 3.5 (OECD, 2022). This is in part the legacy of the guerrilla warfare of the 1960s and 70s where many Colombians were forced from their homes and made internal refugees. From an economic standpoint these differences can be an area of concern due to difficulties in finding macroeconomic strategies that will help all - something that is successful in growing the capital city's, economy is unlikely to work in the poorest region, Choco (OECD, 2022). Therefore, this divide is likely to only increase as the country grows if the nation focuses purely on growth without a significant tilt towards trying to catch the poorer regions up with the rest.

Figure 7:
Homicide rate per 100,000

How Colombia dealt with recent global shocks

The impact of the 2008 Global Financial Crisis on the Colombian economy

Although less exposed to the global financial crisis (GFC) of 2008 than many other countries, the Colombian economy still faced a significant shock, which primarily arose from a contraction in demand for its exports to ailing western economies. The USA is Colombia's largest trading partner, importing 30.9% of all Colombian exports (Workman, 2023), including petroleum, which at 20% of exports is Colombia's most valuable (Department of Commerce International Trade Administration, 2022). In the final six months of 2008, the Europe Brent Spot Price for crude oil fell 74.5% (U.S. Energy Information Administration, 2024), significantly damaging domestic output, tax revenue and employment.

Despite this demand side exposure, the Colombian financial sector had recovered from the domestic financial crisis of the late 1990s (Hernández, López, 2023) and was resilient to the inter-bank debt contagion throughout the GFC, buoyed by stringent regulation and prudential oversight (IMF, 2016). This financial stability helped Colombia avoid negative growth of real GDP (PPP) per capita, registering almost 3% in 2008 and rapidly recovering to nearly 9% in 2009 (Figure 8), helping to grow the economy by 21% between 2008 and 2011 (Figure 10). However, Colombia has underperformed against its closest neighbours Brazil, Peru and Ecuador (Figure 9). From 2000 to 2019, Colombia grew on average 0.48% less than (an average of) Brazil, Peru and Ecuador each year, with total growth falling short of these neighbouring countries by 9.65% in this time period. Lower growth following the GFC was primarily caused by lower consumption and investment – a consequence of declining confidence and greater credit rationing (NU. CEPAL, 2009).

Figure 9:
Difference in real GDP (PPP) per capita growth rate
between Colombia and its closest neighbours

Figure 10:
Real GDP (PPP) per capita (normalised to 2008)

Colombia suffered from increasing inflation for almost all of 2008. Poor weather and strikes constrained the economy's productive capacity (NU. CEPAL, 2009) and a positive bargaining gap from high aggregate demand resulted in inflation peaking at 7.94% in October that year (Figure 11) mostly driven by fuel and food prices - a problem made acute by these goods' price inelasticity in demand and supply. However, Colombia soon benefited from sharp disinflation, with inflation dropping by 4.7 percentage points between 2008 and 2010 to within the target range (Figure 11), despite the minimum wage increasing by 7.7% (NU. CEPAL, 2009) risking greater demand led inflation. This reduction in price level growth witnessed in 2009 was primarily thanks to weaker domestic and international demand for oil and goods (NU. CEPAL, 2009) arising from the global recession, which decreased employment, household income and wealth particularly in western countries causing demand and consequently price for normal goods to fall (McKibbin and Stoeckel, 2009).

Figure 11:
CPI inflation and target inflation rate

**Figure 12:
Inflation and unemployment**

Colombia experienced an uptick in unemployment of 0.9 percentage points between 2008 and 2009 (Figure 12), due to declining demand for sectors such as manufacturing, the minimum wage increase and greater labour participation (NU. CEPAL, 2009). In the same period, inflation decreased by 2.8 percentage points (Figure 12), demonstrating the typical inverse relationship between inflation and unemployment shown by the Phillips Curve. Although this relationship persisted throughout the two decades to 2000, Figure 13 highlights how, since 2000, this inverse relationship has flattened and even reversed – greater unemployment tends to occur alongside higher inflation. Federal Reserve Chairman Jerome Powell has argued that this once widely accepted inverse relationship has become ‘weaker, weaker and weaker,’ because it’s inflation expectations that actually drive inflation and these expectations have become ‘so settled’ (C-SPAN, 2019).

Figure 13
Phillips curve: Inflation against unemployment

Employment data from International Monetary Fund (2023b)
 GDP growth data from Penn World Table (2023)

Colombia's monetary policy response to the 2008 Global Financial Crisis

During the entirety of 2008, the Colombian Peso depreciated by 11.36% against the US Dollar (Dollar Colombia, 2023), with this downwards trend continuing into early 2009, due to lower demand for Colombian exports and currency outflows to the US for the purchasing of Treasury Bonds for their low risk (NU. CEPAL, 2009). This depreciation was soon smoothed out through the greater international competitiveness it produced, FDI it attracted and from central bank intervention, which has become commonplace in recent decades (Vargas, González and Rodríguez, 2013) to smooth out exchange rate volatility, creating greater confidence for firms.

The main monetary policy instrument – Colombia's policy rate – was lowered twice between 2008 and 2011, declining 650 basis points (Figure 14) in a bid to incentivise spending and borrowing. This was further helped by the lowering of reserve requirements for banks (NU. CEPAL, 2009), helping to increase the availability of credit, which particularly benefited individuals who would otherwise be credit excluded or more credit constrained. A low policy rate also helped financial asset prices, as the return on bank-held savings decreased, incentivising the purchase of riskier assets in pursuit of greater return.

Colombia's fiscal policy response to the 2008 Global Financial Crisis

In addition to expansionary monetary policy, Colombia moved away from its typical approach of aiming for primary surpluses to using countercyclical fiscal policy by cutting tax and increasing discretionary spending (Secretariat of the Trade Policy Review, 2012). Corporation tax was cut by one percentage point in 2007 and 2008, bringing it to 33%, in which time revenue from the tax increased by 14.7%. However, the additional revenue from this tax cut was modest, given the rate remained above the average for the world and region (Enache, 2022). Moreover, the tax rate on labour income for the average Colombian remained at 0% - a benefit enjoyed to this day (OECD, 2023b).

Colombia utilised public-private partnerships to invest in infrastructure (The World Bank, 2021), boosting the mobility of labour and goods, whilst creating well-paid jobs – an example of government spending's multiplier effect, as the initial investment by the government triggered further rounds of spending, resulting in an even larger increase in national output. Expected sources of this additional increase may be from extra consumption by people employed in the areas the government invested in and from private sector investment that may have been crowded in by the government's investment.

Automatic stabilisers – fiscal mechanisms which adjust government expenditure and revenue without any direct action from government (Lee and Sheiner, 2019) – such as the Unemployment Subsidy (Carlos, Jairo, Jorge-Andres, 2013), were crucial in counteracting the business cycle and in helping households smooth their consumption, which is beneficial for the poorest, who cannot adequately self-insure.

To boost international competitiveness, Colombia pursued (free) trade agreements with Canada, the EU, US (NU. CEPAL, 2009) and the EFTA (Wüthrich-Bovet, n.d.), which helped diversify its trading partners away from the US and its neighbours, whilst exposing domestic production to greater international competition and lower import prices. This was furthered by tariff reforms

in 2010, which saw the average tariff fall by 4% to 8.2% (Secretariat of the Trade Policy Review Body, 2012).

Colombia's successful policy response is broadly to thank for avoiding recession and managing unemployment, however, Figure 16 demonstrates the downside to these expansionary policies: increasing national debt.

Covid-19 pandemic

Covid-19 had a severe impact on Colombia's economy, with GDP contracting 7.3% in 2020, the worst recession in the nation's history (The World Bank, 2023). Figure 17 shows the pandemic caused a significant increase in poverty, reaching 9.4% of Colombians earning below \$2.15 per day (at 2017 PPP ratios) in 2020, counteracting reductions in levels of poverty that had been achieved over the previous 12 years. Poverty using national criteria also spiked, reaching 42.5% of the population up from 35.7% in 2019 (World Bank, 2023). This is likely caused by the high levels of informal jobs in the Colombian economy. When lockdowns were introduced, those in the informal sector were unable to work, pushing many into poverty (World Bank, 2023).

The demand-side shock caused by Covid-19 led to lower oil prices, as consumers travelled less globally and businesses closed or scaled down production. This meant Colombia suffered a substantial reduction in total goods exports in 2020 from \$40.66 billion in 2019 to \$32.31 billion in 2020 (The World Bank, 2023). *Ceteris paribus*, this decrease in exports would lead to an increased balance of payments deficit putting further strain on the already weakened economy. However, as Colombia's major imports are for use in industry and the country was locked down, the value of imports fell from \$50.52 billion to \$41.18 billion in 2020 more than counteracting the decrease in exports and resulting in a short-term improvement to Colombia's current account deficit (The World Bank, 2023). Overall, in 2020 Colombia's deficit shrank from 4.6% of GDP in 2019 to 3.4%.

As a result of the pandemic, Colombian financial markets were significantly disrupted; public bond and foreign exchange markets lost liquidity, meaning it became harder for investors to buy and sell bonds and currency. This led to uncertainty over the accessibility to foreign funding for

Colombian banks. The combined impact of these events made it difficult for the government to fund any stimulus packages and even its normal expenditure. To combat this, the central bank enacted several measures: it permitted private bonds to be accepted as collateral, increasing loan availability; it also reduced liquidity requirements for commercial banks from 7 to 5%, allowing the banks to create more loans in attempt to maintain consumption and investment. The central bank also took part in asset purchasing, buying back bonds totalling around 11% of the country's monetary base (amount of cash flowing into the economy). These measures stabilised asset markets and increased the number of loans being made by the third quarter of 2020 (Hernando Vargas-Herrera, 2022).

Figure 17:
Poverty headcount ratio at \$2.15 a day (2017 PPP) (% of population)

Macroeconomic challenges faced by Colombia in the future

Migration

Colombia's population of 51 million is expected to peak at approximately 56 million in 2050, predicted by the United Nations (2022). The eventual decline in population is, among many reasons, led by a decrease in the fertility and birth rates within Colombia, as showcased in Figure 18.

However, the most critical factor contributing to the decrease in population is the rise in emigration. Colombia, for most of its recent history, has always had a net negative migration rate - where there are more people leaving Colombia than there are immigrating into it - with an exception during the Covid period. This is highlighted in Figure 19, where the UN expects net migration to remain negative for the rest of the century. This is alarming, as even though the net emigration rate is small compared to Colombia's total population, most emigrants are of working age, leaving the country seeking better economic opportunities. It's often the case that the most skilled workers are drawn away by better wages in neighbouring economies. Figure 20 (OECD, 2016) illustrates how average wages in Colombia compare to others within its region and how Colombia has less than half of the OECD's average yearly earnings.

This data clearly outlines the incentive skilled workers have to migrate, leading to the loss of strong human capital, in the phenomenon referred to as "brain drain" - where highly educated members of the labour force migrate, "draining" the source country of their skills. The sudden increase and decrease in the net migration in Colombia seen in the centre of Figure 19 can also create further demand and supply shocks; however, in the following analysis, the impact of net emigration will be investigated, as the shocks during the 2010s can be argued to be anomalies that are not representative of the long-term trend.

**Figure 19:
Net Migration into Colombia**

**Figure 20:
Comparison of Average
yearly income**

This exodus from Colombia not only results in an outflow from its labour force but also has a greater impact on domestic wage rates and employment. Consider the wage setting model in Figure 21. From its initial equilibrium at point A, an increase in emigration causes the labour force to shrink, shifting LF1 to LF2. Due to labour demand being derived from demand for goods in the economy, a decrease in population will mean there are less people demanding domestic goods, increasing unemployment from point E1 to E2, moving the equilibrium from A to B and in the long run, to point C. This is because at point B, firms are paying wages that are higher than the wage creation curve, so can decrease wages from w_1 to w_2 . Firms also have the choice to lower their prices if they wish to keep their markup constant. If they do choose to keep their markup constant, this would cause deflation, which is undesired as it reduces confidence in the economy. Overall, the model shows how emigration can be a threat to wages and can lead to an increase in the unemployment level in Colombia. This can be devastating and may result in Colombia's government budget being further squeezed to manage such a shock and will decrease the standard of living to those working in Colombia.

Figure 21:
Impact of emigration on the wage
setting model

The effects discussed can be nullified by the existence of trade unions; however, in Colombia there is a distinct lack of trade union power, with only 9.5% of Colombians being in trade unions according to data from the OECD (2018). Similarly, Colombian trade unionists are at risk of homicide as, according to a report by Amnesty International (Amnesty International, 2007), in the period during 1991 to 2006, 2245 trade unionists have been murdered, making it unsafe to identify with a union. Ultimately, this makes the decrease in wages a potent effect as workers have little bargaining power.

Similarly, the overall impacts of brain drain are limited, as workers who have once emigrated, may choose to return to introduce their innovative ideas back into Colombia. By gaining experience in a foreign country, such as the US, Colombians can use it to increase productivity, providing a long-term dividend to make up for the threat emigration poses. Unfortunately, this is unlikely to be true, as the issues discussed earlier make it an undesirable place to conduct business.

Ultimately, emigration poses a large threat to Colombia, by producing downward pressure on wages, and arguably more importantly, the loss of human capital through “brain drain.”

Fossil fuel export dependency

As mentioned earlier Colombia is a major exporter of fuel, making up a combined 43.6% of Colombia's exports. Whilst this is working for Colombia now, allowing it to become a major exporter of fuel due to high global demand, the global shift to renewable energy may change this. With the head of the IEA claiming that "the share of coal, oil and natural gas in the global energy supply, stuck for decades around 80% [is starting] to edge downwards and reaches 73% by 2030", (IEA Executive Summary, 2023), it's predicted that 2030 will be the peak of fossil fuel consumption before the global transition to clean energy, for example the summary states that investment in clean energy has risen by 40% since 2020 and is predicted to rise further. For many countries and the world as a whole this is good news, however for Colombia this paints a new challenge.

As three of Colombia's top five exports are fossil fuels, this is worrying for the Colombian economy, with an estimated 9% of the government's income being fossil fuel related (Rubiano, 2023). If the fossil fuel industry continues declining, there will be a large cut in government income, making Colombia less likely to invest in important infrastructure projects to produce green energy. In an attempt to cut fossil fuel consumption, the coal mines in the La Jagua de Ibrico region were closed, causing a loss of 7000 jobs, meaning over 95% of the workers in this area were out of a job. This led to nearly 100 restaurants, cafes and hotels closing. According to the town's mayor, over 85% of the income in the region was lost, devastating the area (Morales, 2022). The residents argued the multinationals which came to the area to exploit the coal have not done enough to develop the area around the mines to survive when the mines close, as almost all of the workers in this area were miners, this left them occupationally immobile, as the mines shut down they now lack the skills required to take up other work due to being specialised in the coal mining industry (Morales, 2022). As global demand for coal continues to decrease, this issue will only become more widespread, if mines continue to close more jobs are likely threatened and crime rates are likely to rise, leading to further cartel activity in Colombia as those out of a job often turn to cartels to make a better life for themselves.

Whilst green energy poses a problem to the fossil fuel exporting Colombia, this is not the only issue with relying on fossil fuels for their income.

Figure 22:
US Central Appalachian Coal prices 1991-2021

As seen in Figure 22, coal prices are especially volatile, with prices falling from \$72.84 in 2018 to around \$42.77 in 2020. As coal makes up such a large proportion of Colombia’s exports, it can represent an issue for government revenue, making it hard for Colombia to plan long term investments. If for example, the USA goes into recession and demand for fuel falls, the value of exports falls, leading to trade imbalances and hurting the economic stability in Colombia.

Figure 23:
Percentage GDP growth 1961-2022

As seen in Figure 23, the GPD growth in Colombia is volatile, mostly due to their exports of fossil fuels and agricultural produce, with the pandemic effecting Colombia harder than other countries due to their reliance on exporting fuel. During the pandemic, fuel prices fell to a 20 year low of below \$20 per barrel (Dharshini, 2020), with some prices even going as low as minus \$37.63 (Bloomberg, 2023) per barrel in the West Texas Intermediate, causing Colombia’s GDP to fall 7.6% in a year. Whilst Covid impacted almost all countries, it impacted oil exporting countries the hardest, as global demand for fuel fell by 8% during Covid - the largest fall in global fuel demand since WWII. Whilst Colombia recovered quickly from the pandemic, with a GDP increase of 10.4% in 2021, this still represents how much Colombia relies on the state of the world for their economy. Colombia’s reliance on oil can pose an issue for them, if there is a dependency on one

sole buyer of their exports, this can leave them very vulnerable to changes in trade patterns and the economic state of other countries aside from their own. This is especially true for Colombia as the USA and China import \$11.7B and \$3.69B of goods, respectively.

The reliance on exploiting natural resources poses a threat to Colombia's economy, because of this Colombia may struggle to integrate into a renewable energy future, without significant investment in training and construction of renewables projects Colombia's economy is destined to collapse when fossil fuels are no longer demanded.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Colombia shows steady GDP growth and primary sector export strengths. However, the nation struggles with challenges, such as income inequality, dependence on specific exports such as fossil fuels, and the impact of migration on its labour force. This report highlights the need for diversified economic strategies, inclusive policies to address income inequality, and a proactive approach toward transitioning to sustainable energy sources. Colombia's future prosperity hinges on navigating these challenges effectively and embracing strategies that promote both economic growth and social development.

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